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INDEX

Sr. No.	Name of the Research Paper	Author	Page No.
1.	Industrial Disaster : A Case Study of Bhopal Gas Leak Disaster	Neeru Sharma	1-2
2.	Food Status in Drought Prone Areas of Rajasthan : A Study based on Agro-Climatic Regions	Dr. Vinod Kumar Somvir Bhorla	3-8
3.	Stone Tools, Technology in Ancient India	Parveen Kumar	9-12
4.	Impact Assessment Study of Rural Road Connectivity Under PMGSY - A Case Study	Ravin Kumar, Suman Bajiya	13-18
5.	Declining Sex Ratio in Haryana	Dr. Urmila Sabharwal	19-21
6.	An Analysis of Growth Rate and Sex Ratio of Haryana, 2001-2011	Priyanka, Poonam Rani, Sachin	22-25
7.	Land Use/Land Cover Change in the Buffer Zone of Nimbaheera Cement Industries Region, Chittorgarh, Rajasthan	Satyapal Jiterwal	26-29
8.	Need and Perspectives of Sustainable Development in Indian Scenario	Rahul Choudhary	30-33
9.	Employment Pattern in Rural Haryana : An Analysis	Mrs. Mamta Nandal Mrs. Kavita Vpo Rukhi	34-37
10.	Recent Trend, Pattern and Characteristics of Crime against Women in India : 2004-14	Naveen Kumar Dr. Naresh Malik Subhi Gaur	38-42
11.	Sustainable Urban Waste Management in India	Dr. Anil Kumar	43-47
12.	Crop Diversification Pattern in Haryana	Neelam Garg and Savita	48-51
13.	Environment and Landuse of Rasikbeel Complex	Subhashis Biswas	52-57
14.	Water Table Fluctuation in Rewari District, Haryana : A Geographical Analysis	Vinay Kumar, Pardeep Kumar	58-62
15.	Evolution of Party System in India and Alliance Performance in Parliamentary Election, 2009	Sunil	63-66
16.	Water Insufficiency and Its Management: A Challenge for India	Neetu Singh	67-70
17.	Identification of Backwardness in Mewat: A Study Based on Socio- Economic Aspects of Development	Shiv Kumar, Babita	71-77
18.	Climate Change Strategies and Development	Dr. Sushma Redhu	78-80
19.	The Need of Hour: Balance Between Development and Environment	Sanjeev Kumar Chaudhary	81-85
20.	Farmers Suicide in India: Causes and Remedies	Sajjan Kumar	86-91
21.	Development and Environment	Poonam	92-94
22.	Sustainable Development: Need of the hour	Dr. Manisha	95-96
23.	Irrigation Expansion and Change in Cropping Pattern in Panipat District	Partibha and Satesh Kalkal	97-104
24.	Regional Disparity in Availability of Electricity in India	Praveen Kumar	105-110
25.	Depleting Natural Resources-A Threat To Sustainability	Dr. Pardeep Malik & Dr. Anju	111-112
26.	Urban Sprawl: A Critique For Sustainable Development of National Capital Region (NCR Delhi)	Anil Malik	113-116

Stone Tools, Technology in Ancient India

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Millions of year age our ancestor began littering the African landscape with stone and bones tools. From the first tools to today's glass bottles is the dominant component of the archaeological record. The material retrieved from excavation and exploration needs to be classified into types and styles on the basis of objective and descriptive attribute clusters. Finally when these objects are arranged in chronological order, many significant information regarding culture change and evolution start becoming apparent. To use a modern culture example we can have pots, pans, ladles etc can be broadly grouped into a cluster as 'cooking object'. Likewise reading and writing objects, sleeping objects, transport objects etc., can all be formed to reflect upon the relative specialization and pre-occupation of certain functions in the society (Sankalia, 1974). In pre-history, unfortunately, no indication in the object themselves and we have to depend on stone tools (Sankalia, H.D. 1970:1).

Tools:

The stone tools which were fabricated by man constitute the main bulk of culture material recovered from as earliest time to 5000 years ago. This does not mean that man did not fashion tools from wood or bones as well (Bhattacharya, 1979). Apparently the organic medium on which man have possibly made tools did not stand the test of time. From around 35000 years, bones are recovered along with the stones but any possible attempts on this material made by man earlier to this date have been destroyed forever (Agarwal, 1984). The usual tool types and the cultural stages defined on them are given below.

Paleolithic

Duration	Broad Tool Categories	Mode	Tool Types	Cultural Divisions
2.8 million years	Pebble tools and flakes	i	Cleavers, Handaxe, Chopper, Chopping tool, Clactonian flakes	Lower Paleolithic
100,000 - 80,000 BC	Flake tools	ii	Side scrapers, Knives, Points, Awls	Middle Paleolithic
40,000- 10,000 BC	Blade and Bone Tools	iii	Blade, Burins, End Scrapers, Bone harpoons, Needles	Upper Paleolithic

Mesolithic

Likewise Mesolithic (10,000-6000 BC) is defined on the basis of several tool types made on tiny blades often referred to as micro-liths. These are 3-5cm long, 1-1.5cm broad and 0.5-0.2cm thick blades which have been skillfully detached by pressure flaking technique (Bhattacharya, 2010:1). These are blunted along one border are mounted on adze-like handles to form composite tools. One of the significant inventions of this period is the construction of bows and arrows, the latter with micro-liths attached to form the tip.

Neolithic

During Neolithic (6000-4000 BC) big axes appear with surfaces perfectly smoothed by laborious rubbing on stones with sand and water. Thus, we see that the various cultural stages are discernible on the basis of type identification alone. It is not very surprising, therefore, that stones age typology forms a fundamental aspect of research for archaeologist of this period.

Techniques:

There are a number of tool techniques prevalent during the pre-historic period i.e. Stone Age and these are discussed below in detail:

A. Block-on-Block Technique:-

Though in India we have not a very clear-cut stratigraphic development in the flaking of stone tools, the earliest and the most widespread was the Block-on-Block or Anvil Technique. Tools of this technique have been recovered from Hoshangabad and Maheshwar and in Sohan, the Indus, and the Banganga and in the Liddar Valley. Huge Flaks with prominent bulbs of percussion were most probably the result of striking one large pebble or boulder against another. Their age is early to Middle Pleistocene.

B. Stone Hammer Technique:-

In the Stone Hammer Technique, the artificer took one round or ovalish pebble and struck against the periphery of the other, kept in his right or left hand as the case may be. This was continued, often striking on alternate sides, until a sharp wavy edge, as desired was produced.

Block-on-Block Technique

Stone Hammer Technique

C. Controlled or Step-Method Technique:-

This was followed by the controlled or Step-Method of flaking. Briefly, the flake scars are smaller. Shallower and leave a step-like mark, as the blows do not go much deeper, and are against the body of the tool. The longitudinal profile of many hand axes as well as cleavers is found trimmed in this way.

D. Cylinder Hammer Technique:-

In the Cylinder Hammer Technique, the artificer took one hand was struck by a cylindrical hammer of stone, bone or hard wood. Small flakes from the tools were removed and finally a tool prepared. The flake scars are very shallow and small.

Cylinder Hammer Technique

E. Prepared Core and Platform Technique:-

Then came a highly ingenious technique. It is called prepared core and platform technique or the Levalloisian technique after the type site in France. This technique was certainly practiced in the closing stage of the Early Stones Age and such tools were very common on the Stone Age sites on India. In this technique a single, comparatively thin flake-round, oval or triangular removes with carefully work on the core, and prepare the platform. The blow should usually at an angle of 90°. Though it must be emphasize that the prepare platform. As a result of this technique symmetrical fairly thin flake were obtained.

F. Clactonian Technique:-

In this technique a nodule is selected which has fairly regular surfaces intersecting or meeting in a ridge. Such a ridge is normally found in a flat river pebble. It is usually dull and may be rounded, but in the case of a pebble or nodule broken naturally, there might be a sharp edge.

Having selected such a nodule, a blow gave with another stone the edge of one of the plain surfaces. If this blow is well directed and of suitable strength, quite a good flake will be detached.

G. Levallois Technique:-

A more advanced, artistic and skilful method of preparing flakes and cores is Levallois Technique. It was first noticed at Levallois Perret, Paris. Hence the technique has been often described as 'Levalloisian'.

In this method instead of straightaway hit one flattish pebble or core with another pebble and the result of it a comparatively thin flake, roughly triangular or oval outline. It had a clean undersurface, and a part of the prepared platform form an angle of about 80°-90° with the undersurface. The undersurface should ordinarily bear shallow triangular centrally directed flake scars indicating previous preparation of the core. It required little or no subsequent retouch because its edge was already sharp due to previous preparation.

In the Punjab, De Terra and Paterson noticed that flakes with Levalloisian character appear only in the Late Soan A, during the Third Glacial times (Terra, H. De. and T.T. Paterson, 2003).

H. Grinding and Polishing Technique:-

Lastly we have the technique called 'Grinding and Polishing'. In this a pebble or nodule or a block of stone, preferably dyke basalt, or diorite, was first flaked by the stone hammer, control and pressure techniques, if necessary, a fairly uniform surface was achieved. Then followed pecking by which all uneven surface were removed with a chisel-like tool. Then, this partly finished tool was ground in boat-shaped sandstone or rough-surfaced querns, with a little water and abrasives, though these are not quite necessary, if the surface is rough. Gradually the surface was smoothed. Since the man at this time was more particular about the edge part, this was further ground, until it become perfectly smooth and perhaps with a little addition of some oily substance, the surface was made glistening. Thus were made the pointed but axes (or Celt), chisels and other wood-working tools of the New Stone Age. In India its principal at home was Andhra, Mysore, Madras, then South Eastern U.P., Assam and Burzahom in Kashmir and now found in the East and West Punjab at a number of sites. In the latter, the stone used is not as hard as in the South. They are made on soft stone. In Eastern India, Assam particularly, shouldered Celts were made by wire-cutting (Dani, 1960).

I. Blade - Flake Technique:-

The Blade-Flake, pressure and Crested Ridge techniques are in a sense related because the main aim was to produce a thin flake, the length of which was more than its breadth, known as blade.

In the earliest to be discovered was the blade-flake technique. The characteristic blade-flake is long and comparatively narrow with more or less parallel edges. Such blade-flakes are occasionally found in Early and Middle Stone Age cultures, but regularly in the Upper Palaeolithic culture or the true blade-flake cultures. It was at this time, it is believed, that the proper technique for obtaining blade-flake was discovered.

J. Crested Ridge Technique:-

In this technique, all the irregularities or whatever could be easily removed by a round stone hammer. Secondly, a ridge was prepared along the length of the prepared core by alternate flaking. This ridge is supposed either to guide the regular removal of parallel-edged flakes or it creates a line of weakness which makes it easy for the removal of the first series of flakes.

Such crested ridge flakes and cores still having a ridge on them are found in the Harappan and Later Chalcolithic cultures and it is believed that for the mass production of blades this was a very convenient technique (Subbarao and Sankalia et al. 1958)

K. Pressure Flake Technique:-

Thin, long, slender blades were also removed by a pressure technique (Sankalia, 1964:34). It was not specialized in form, but a rough flake on which there was somewhere a thick, more or less rectangular, edge. By holding the fabricator in one hand and placing its end against the edge of the blade which was to be blunted exerting pressure, little flakes could be pushed off very rapidly and with particularly no risk of snapping the blade.

It was by a kind of pressure-flaking again that very thin, flat flakes were removed from the surface of a blade in order to trim it into a lance-head or arrow head (Sankalia, 1964).

Pressure Flake Technique

Conclusion:-

The term 'stone tools' can technically refer to the study of any anthropogenic stone object, but in its usual sense it is applied to archaeological material which can be associated with pre-historic period. A holistic understanding of the lithic reduction and ground stone processes, in combination with the use of statistics, can allow us to draw conclusions concerning the type of lithic manufacturing techniques used by pre-historic peoples. These data can then be used to draw an understanding of socioeconomic and cultural organization.

The best known stone tool techniques and typology in India were defined by H.D. Sankalia (1982) on the basis of manufacturing techniques and morphological characteristics. During the Palaeolithic period, Block-on-Block, Stone Hammer, Step-Method, Prepared Core and Platform, Clactonian, Levallois were used to manufacture tools. In the Mesolithic Prepared Core and Platform, Blade-Flake Technique, Crested Ridge, Pressure Flake was used to fabricate micro-lithic. Grinding and Polishing technique was used during the Neolithic period to make tools.

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